

CURRENT STATE OF SUPPLYING THE POPULATION WITH AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

In this work, detailed information is given about the process of water conservation and efficient operation of agricultural products and modern technologies. Information on promising varieties and their indicators is provided. A detailed understanding of the technological parameters of cultivation of necessary agricultural products is given.

Key words: variety, technology, yield, economy, economic efficiency.

In the Decree No. 5853 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the approval of the strategy of the development of agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period of 2020-2030", it is stated that "to ensure the safety of food products and to improve the consumption ration, to develop a state policy of food security, which provides for the cultivation of the required amount of food products exit and treatment" are defined as the priority directions of strategy implementation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to select wheat varieties suitable for the climatic conditions of the region, with high grain quality and breadability, and to improve the agrotechnology of their cultivation [1]. 1 million in Uzbekistan in 1991. tons of grain was grown, this year 8 mln. It reached more than a ton. Productivity in 2020 is 1 mln. More than 77 thousand hectares, 6 million of them. 400,000 tons of crops were harvested, with an average of 57.5 centners per two hectares [2]. Information is provided on the creation of existing conditions in the soil, their development, and the development of plants [16].

Today, cereal production is the main branch of crop science, and wheat is the staple food for about 40% of the world's population and provides about 25% of the population's energy needs.

China, India, Russia, USA and Canada are the top five wheat growing countries in the world. Wheat is grown in these countries on the basis of accelerated advanced technologies, and the average yield in the world is 3.1 tons per hectare. Although wheat grain and flour products are the most important sources of calories, the amount of protein and minerals in wheat grain grown today is much lower. Like many basic food products, due to the small amount of iron content in wheat grain, as a result of iron deficiency in the main layer of our country, about two billion people worldwide suffer from iron deficiency.

Along with increasing the production of wheat grain in our republic, it is crucial to enrich the grain with elements important for human health. In order to eliminate the symptoms caused by iron deficiency in plants, it is possible to increase the growth and development of plants, improve grain quality, and increase the yield of soft wheat by using multifunctional preparations with high iron content.

According to G. Maslov, G. Nebavskiy, the main scientific essence of resource-efficient technology is to increase the amount of organic matter in the soil and improve the water and aeration regime due to the use of decayed and undecayed remains of plants in the surface layer of the soil as mulch [3,4]. According to A.Nurbekov's experiments, the number of grasses that sprouted in the fall in two years in the Republic of Karakalpakstan was 10% lower in the fields where direct resource-efficient sowing was used, compared to the fields planted in the traditional way. On the other hand, increasing grain cultivation in our country and increasing the productivity of irrigated areas is directly related to the planting of wheat varieties suitable for certain soil and climatic conditions. Productivity depends on the technology of cultivation of this type of agriculture.

In this regard, it is urgent to carry out research on modern scientifically based methods of irrigation of water and resources, as well as improvement of land reclamation [5].

In our republic, in the following years, depending on the soil and climatic conditions of each soil and climate, it is necessary to obtain a stable abundant harvest with high yield, ensure food safety, and develop agrotechnical measures by developing the timing of planting winter wheat, the method of irrigation, and the application and norms of mineral fertilizers during its development period. Special attention is paid to timely implementation. Here, the issue of working with new varieties, adapting them to their cultivated areas and achieving high productivity is becoming urgent [6,7].

Special attention is paid to the development and regular improvement of agrotechnics for the cultivation of field crops, taking into account the biological characteristics of field crops, soil and climatic conditions, in order to satisfy the demand of the population for food products, industry for raw materials, and animal husbandry for feed.

Research on growing ecologically clean, abundant and high-quality products from agricultural crops, planting crops that preserve the soil fertility of repeated crops in areas freed from autumn grain crops, and obtaining additional grain yield is urgent. At the same time, new works are being carried out for the formation of other agricultural crops [8].

Experiments show that after harvesting winter wheat, on average, 3.0-3.5 tons of roots and stalk remains in the field. 12-13 kg of nitrogen, 5-6 kg of phosphorus, 18-20 kg of potassium are accumulated in 1 ton of root and stem residue of winter wheat. 3.0-3.5 tons of manure left in the field returns to the soil in the form of 36-45 kg of nitrogen, 15-21 kg of phosphorus, and 54-70 kg of potassium. Moss planted in winter wheat leaves 1.8-2.8 tons of organic matter per hectare, and soybean leaves 2.5-2.8 tons of organic matter per hectare.

According to the results of agrochemical analysis, 27.5 kg of nitrogen, 13.2 kg of phosphorus, 270 kg of potassium are found in 1 ton of mosh roots and roots, and 17.5 of nutrients in 1 ton of soybean; 5.7; 13.5 kg is collected. If the organic residue of mosh is 2.3 tons per hectare on average, 63.2 kg of nitrogen, 30.3 kg of phosphorus, 62.1 kg of potassium per hectare, when the organic residue of soybean is 2.6 tons per hectare, 45.5 kg of nitrogen, 14.8 kg of phosphorus and 35.1 kg of potassium return to the soil [10, 11]. As a result of planting repeated and intermediate crops in short-row rotation systems, organic residues accumulate in the amount of 5-6 tons per hectare in one season. This, in turn, ensures an increase in the amount of humus in the soil by 80-85 kg/ha, nitrogen by 55-60 kg/ha, phosphorus by 15-20 kg/ha, potassium by 55-60 kg/ha, and the annual amount of nitrogen used for growing crops in the next season. It allows to reduce potassium by 25-30% and 45-

50%. In cotton-cereal short-row cropping systems, the grain yield of winter wheat increases by 15-20%, and the yield of cotton increases by 10-15% [12-15].

Depending on the types of repeated crops, legumes (beans, soybeans, lentils, beans), grains (rice, millet, corn, white corn, sugar corn, sorghum), oilseeds (linseed, peanuts, soybeans, sesame, sunflower, sorghum), roots and tubers (sugar beets, beets, beets, carrots, radishes, turnips, potatoes, etc.), fodder (maize, oats, buckwheat, oats, rye, triticale, peas, perco and etc.), vegetables (cabbage, cucumber, melon, watermelon, tomato, squash, etc.) are divided into crops. When they are grown as a repeated crop, 2-3 harvests are obtained from the same area in one year, a nutritious fodder base is created for livestock, conditions are created for maintaining and increasing soil fertility, and a clean ecological environment is created. On the other hand, intercrops yield up to 250-450 quintals of green mass per hectare, depending on planting dates, feeding rate and biological characteristics of the crop.

This makes it possible to grow vitamin-rich and juicy additional fodder, increase the production of eggs, meat and milk. Therefore, special attention should be paid to planting catch crops along with fodder crops in well-watered areas.

The seeds of catch crops are sown in well-prepared fields using grain drills. Rye 100-150 kg per hectare, barley 120-130 kg, oats 90-100 kg, rapeseed, perco, mustard 12-15 kg, corn 50-60 kg, chickpeas 120-150 kg, rye or triticale chickpeas together with peas When planting rye and triticale, 50-60 kg, chickpea 100-120 kg, when planting with rye, triticale, oats, rapeseed, perco or mustard, 70-80 kg of seed is used for the first, and 80-90 kg for the second. Repeated crops are planted in wide rows or scattered in late June and early July. As a repeated crop, the distance between rows of mosh is 60 cm, the planting pattern is 60x20, 60x15, and the planting rate is 250,000-400,000 pieces per hectare. The planting depth is 3-4 cm. Soybean planting scheme is 60x5, 70x3, if the row spacing is 60 cm, 60-80 kg of seeds are used per hectare. The planting depth is 4-5 cm. Beans are planted 60-70 cm between rows. The planting depth is 4-6 cm. 80-120 kg of seeds are used per hectare. Millet is planted in a scheme of 45x15 or 60x15 cm. The planting depth is 3-4 cm. 12-16 kg of seeds are used per hectare. Maize is planted in wide rows, with a row spacing of 60, 70, 90 cm. The rate of sowing is 25-30 kg/ha when it is planted for grain, and 45-50 kg/ha when it is planted for fodder. The planting depth is 6-7 cm.

So, when winter wheat and repeated leguminous grain crops are planted in its wake, mung bean and soybean, the organic residues they leave in the soil are on average 4-5 tons per hectare, and through them 70-100 kg of nitrogen, 30-40 kg of phosphorus, 60-100 kg of potassium. substances return to the soil. This creates conditions for replenishment of nutrients absorbed by plants from the soil, maintenance and increase of soil fertility, high and high-quality production of technical plants (cotton) [9].

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